

RESULTS OF HISTOLOGICAL EXAMINATION OF PATIENTS WHO UNDERWENT SURGICAL TREATMENT FOR A RUPTURE OF THE LONG HEAD TENDON OF THE BICEPS BRACHII

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Abstract. *The long tendon of the biceps brachii plays a crucial role in the functional state of the arm, and accompanying inflammatory or degenerative-destructive processes in the joint are significant in its ruptures. Determining which process is active in patients allows for the application of appropriate treatment. Objective: To identify histopathological changes in the tendon structure in patients with ruptures of the long head of the biceps tendon. The article describes histomorphological changes in the tendon tissue of 20 male patients with an average age of 58 who underwent surgery for long head of the biceps tendon rupture at the clinic of the Republican Specialized Scientific and Practical Medical Center of Traumatology and Orthopedics from 2022 to 2024. Eight patients in the first group underwent tendon fixation under arthroscopic control, while 12 patients in the second group underwent traditional subpectoral and suprapectoral fixation. Results were evaluated using the Constant-Murley Scale and R.K. Gupta methodology. Tendon tissue was histologically examined using standard Hematoxylin and Eosin, as well as Trichrome and Alcian blue stains. The condition of the tendon tissue was assessed using the Bonar scale. Patients in both groups showed a relative decrease in pain and an increase in range of motion after surgical treatment. At 6 and 12-months follow-up, 16 patients showed excellent results and 4 showed good results. Histological analysis of the tendon using the Bonar scale revealed predominantly chronic degenerative changes, characterized by high rates of myxoid degeneration (an increase in the volume of ground substance) and alterations in collagen fibers. Histopathological examination of ruptured long head of the biceps tendon revealed changes characteristic of tendinosis rather than tendinitis. In the postoperative period, all patients demonstrated good to excellent outcomes.*

Keywords: *histology, biceps brachii, long head, rupture, surgical treatment.*

Introduction

Traumatic rupture of the long head tendon of the biceps brachii often leads to pain and instability in the anterior region of the shoulder joint. The proximal part of the biceps brachii muscle originates from two tendons, with the short head starting from the coracoid process of the scapula, while the long head begins from the supraglenoid tubercle of the scapula and the superior

glenoid labrum. The distal portion attaches to the radial tuberosity of the radius. The influence of the biceps brachii on arm function is debatable, but it is considered significant in complex movements, including strong forearm supination, weak elbow flexion, and maintaining shoulder joint stability.

The majority of biceps brachii ruptures involve the long head of its proximal part. In some cases, such ruptures are accompanied by pathologies like SLAP lesions, rotator cuff injuries, tendinitis, and tenosynovitis. Patients often complain of pain, reduced arm strength, and noticeable deformity. Diagnosis is based on the patient's history of injury and the presence of the pathognomonic "Popeye" sign in clinical examination. Currently, ultrasound examination is also becoming increasingly popular, demonstrating high accuracy.

Surgical treatment of the long head tendon of the biceps brachii is becoming increasingly relevant with the development of modern medicine. Surgical intervention includes various fixation methods and choices of fixation sites, with anchor fixation considered superior to other methods due to its high level of biomechanical stability. Patients who undergo surgery exhibit restoration of muscle shape, strength, and tendon tension.

Sometimes, contraindications to surgical treatment necessitate conservative management. Patients receive non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs, corticosteroid injections, and physiotherapy. This group primarily consists of elderly patients, often with a history of prolonged rheumatic disease or chronic cardiovascular and respiratory conditions. These patients suffer for the rest of their lives with pronounced deformity in the arm area and a sharp decrease in arm strength.

One of the important factors in the rupture of the long head tendon of the biceps brachii is degenerative-destructive processes in the joint, as well as microtraumas. This is usually accompanied by rotator cuff tears, labral damage, acromioclavicular joint pathology, and shoulder osteoarthritis. There are several theories on the origin of degenerative-destructive processes in the tendon, among which circulatory disorders, inflammation, and recurrent microtraumas during shoulder movement provide more convincing evidence than others. One or more of these conditions contribute to the development of the disease pathogenesis.

Histological examination of the tendon in biceps tendinitis and tendinopathy revealed the following changes: chronic inflammatory process, fibrosis, myxoid degeneration, disorganization of collagen fibers, changes in vascularization, and alterations in tenocyte morphology.

Surgical restoration of tendon integrity in long head biceps tendon ruptures has several advantages, allowing patients to continue an active, painless lifestyle. The presence of a degenerative-destructive background in non-traumatic tendon ruptures highlights the importance of treating tendinitis and tendinopathy in disease prevention. Accurate detection of changes in tendon structure allows for correct and effective treatment, which subsequently reduces the likelihood of rupture.

Materials and methods

From 2020 to 2024, 21 patients underwent surgical treatment for rupture of the long head of the biceps tendon at the clinic of the Republican Specialized Scientific and Practical Medical Center of Surgery. All patients were male, with an average age of 58 years, ranging from 31 to 65 years.

Clinical examinations revealed that patients reported experiencing pain in the anterior shoulder for an extended period and sustaining a recent injury, after which they noticed limited

arm movement, decreased arm strength, and deformity. Clinical examination revealed the "Popeye" sign in patients. Additionally, each patient experienced subjective weakness and pain during forearm supination when the elbow was flexed to 90 degrees. In addition to general clinical examinations, patients underwent shoulder joint radiography, electroneuromyography, and ultrasound examinations. The rupture of the long head of the biceps tendon was confirmed by MRI in all patients.

Cases of concomitant pathology or instability of the shoulder joint were excluded from this study.

Patients underwent surgery using two different methods: the first group of patients (9) underwent tendon fixation under arthroscopic control, while the second group of patients (12) underwent tendon fixation using the traditional method, either subpectoral or suprapectoral. In 10 patients, the tendon was sutured to the bicipital groove with lavsan threads, in 7 patients with an interference screw, and in 4 patients with anchors. In 18 patients, the tendon was fixed to the bicipital groove, while subpectoral tenodesis was performed in 3 patients.

To comprehensively assess the function of the shoulder and elbow joints, the shoulder function evaluation chart recommended by the European Society for Surgery of the Shoulder and Elbow in 1990 (Constant C.R., Murley A.N., 1987) was used. Since the biceps is a two-joint muscle, when assessing its function, attention should be paid to the restoration of range of motion in the elbow and shoulder joints, the appearance of the arm, the presence or absence of complications during examination, and the subjective and objective characteristics of arm strength. In this regard, it is advisable to use the Constant-Murley Scale assessment system and R.K. Gupta's methodology.

Evaluation of treatment outcomes using the Constant-Murley and R.K. Gupta scales: Excellent outcomes - over 300 points; good outcomes - in the range of 251 to 300 points; satisfactory outcomes - from 201 to 250 points; unsatisfactory outcomes - 200 points or less.

After surgical treatment, the patients' excised tendon tissue underwent special histological examination. Standard hematoxylin and eosin stains were used for the histological examination. Additionally, Trichrome stain was used to detect fibrosis, and Alcian blue was used to detect myxoid degeneration.

The condition of the tendon tissue was assessed using the Bonar scale. According to this scale, tissue was evaluated from 0 to 3 points based on 5 indicators: A. Changes in tenocyte morphology. B. Increased tenocyte cellularity. C. Increased vascularization. D. Increase in ground substance volume. E. Disruption of collagen fiber arrangement. The aforementioned indicators were assessed based on their absence (0), mild presence (1), moderate presence (2), and marked presence (3). In this case, a minimum score of 0 points indicates the absence of any pathological processes in the tendon, while a maximum score of 15 points indicates the most severe pathological changes.

Results

After all patients underwent surgery, they got up and began to move independently the next day. One day after surgery, patients began to move their fingers, and after one week, they started moving their elbow joints. After 1 month of splint fixation, the range of motion in the shoulder and elbow joint was restored to 70-80%. The average length of hospitalization for patients was 5 days.

No intraoperative complications were observed in any of the patients who underwent surgery. In the postoperative period, no signs of inflammation were detected in the wound, and no neurological changes in hand movements and sensations were observed. Two patients were re-examined one month after surgery, where pain was detected in the operative area, and the patients were prescribed non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs, enzyme preparations, and physiotherapy. One patient received a local corticosteroid injection after these procedures, after which no other pain syndrome was observed. No repeated tendon rupture was observed in any of the patients during the follow-up period.

Patients underwent follow-up examinations at 1 month, 6 months, and 12 months after surgery. When evaluating patients using the Constant-Murley Scale and R.K. Gupta method, excellent results were observed in 15 patients, good results in 4 patients, and satisfactory results in 1 patient in the first month after surgery. At 6 months and 12 months of follow-up, 16 patients showed excellent results and 4 patients showed good results.

The results of the histological examination of the patients are presented in the following table:

	Score				Average
	0	1	2	3	
Changes in tenocyte morphology		12	7	1	1.45±0.4
Increased cellularity of tenocytes		14	6		1.3±0.4
Increased vascularization	3	13	1	3	1.2±0.6
Increase in the volume of the ground substance		6	11	3	1.85±0.5
Disturbances in the direction of collagen fibers		4	15	1	1.85±0.6
Total					7.65±1.8

Histological analysis of the tendon using the Bonar scale revealed that changes in the tendon tissue were predominantly chronic degenerative in nature, characterized by increased myxoid degeneration (increased volume of the ground substance) and changes in collagen fibers (1.85±0.5; 1.85±0.6). The results of the study showed that the inflammatory process was rare (3). In these cases, the examination also revealed a minimal number of inflammatory cells.

Figure 1. 2 Histopathological images A. Normal tendon B. Increase in the volume of the main substance/mucin C. Normal tendon D. Disruption and loss of normal parallel arrangement of

collagen fibers B. Increase in the volume of the main substance /mucine C. Normal tendon; D. Disruption and loss of normal parallel arrangement of collagen fibers

Discussion

Histopathological analysis following tenodesis of the long head of the biceps tendon did not reveal signs of acute inflammatory process. Inflammatory events were rare, predominantly mild, focal, and chronic in nature. No clear correlation was found between the severity of histopathological changes in the tendon and the improvement of postoperative clinical outcomes. The main histopathological changes consisted of disruption of collagen structure and myxoid degeneration, indicating the predominance of degenerative processes over inflammatory ones in the development of the disease.

Recently, Nuelle et al. analyzed the presence of regional histological changes in the resected long head of the biceps tendon, dividing it into three parts (proximal, middle, and distal). The authors found that the Bonar scores of the proximal part were significantly higher than those of the distal part, which they attributed to regional tenosynovitis, i.e., a local focus of inflammation and a source of pain. Unfortunately, the correlation was weak for all three sections (proximal $r=0.08$; middle $r=0.03$; distal $r=0.1$) and no visible signs of inflammation were observed; instead, only synovial hypertrophy and hyperplasia were detected.

This study confirms the main histopathological findings of previous studies. These results show that the most frequently observed pathological changes in the analyzed tendons include the accumulation of mucoid/myxoid substance and fibrotic (collagen) changes, while the inflammatory process is minimal. Similar results were described by Zabrzinski et al. They examined histological specimens of the long head of the biceps tendon from 35 shoulders and found significant disorganization of collagen fibers, scattered tenocytes, and significant degeneration of the ground substance. Furthermore, in most cases (32 out of 35), despite the presence of positive clinical tests for biceps pathology, no signs of inflammation were identified in conjunction with degenerative tendon processes. Studies did not reveal any significant histological differences among the three segmental regions of the long head of the biceps tendon. On the contrary, the authors observed relatively uniform morphological changes throughout the tendon. General histomorphological features indicate that this is not an inflammatory process, but rather a holistic tendinosis. Our research confirms the conclusions of other scientists describing chronic tendon degeneration and a lack of inflammation. After tendon injury, inflammation may play an important role in the initial period, but later, the inflammatory process plays a negligible role in tendon rupture or no role at all.

One of the issues that deserves further discussion is the methods of fixation. There are cadaveric studies comparing the onlay and inlay techniques of tenodesis of the long head of the biceps tendon using anchor fixation in the upper part of the bicipital groove. The ability to withstand the target load in the inlay group slightly surpassed the onlay technique (215N versus 210N). In another cadaveric study conducted by Tashjian and colleagues, different methods of fixation for the long head of the biceps tendon tenodesis were compared. They analyzed the biomechanical advantage of two anchors and an interference screw as fixation methods and found that the interference screws have a higher load-bearing capacity, but the anchors can better withstand tension. A clinical study retrospectively examined patients who underwent long head of the biceps tendon tenodesis with an interference screw or anchors, suggesting that fixation with the interference screw may have clinical advantages. When examining 88 patients, no significant

difference was observed in either the construct, VAS pain scale, ASES, or Constant scores. However, pain syndrome in the area of the bicipital groove was observed in only one patient in the interference screw group and in four patients in the anchor fixation group. Another study by the same author reported complications after long head of the biceps tendon tenodesis with an interference screw, which included 491 patients who underwent the same tenodesis technique, and only 12 cases (2.4%) reported complications. In one case, a serious complication was observed, such as a fracture of the proximal humerus at the tenodesis site, in eight cases there was re-rupture of the tendons, in two cases there were mild strains, and in one case, the screw had to be removed and re-fixed due to its prominence.

There are several issues associated with using the Bonar histopathological assessment system. First, there are difficulties in correlating the Bonar scale with clinical and radiological features. Second, while the original Bonar scale only evaluated four characteristics, many authors use a modified five-point version, complicating comparisons. Third, information about the number of researchers who participated in studies using the Bonar scale or their level of experience is often not provided. Finally, researchers typically randomly select a specific part of the tendon for evaluation, which limits the standardization process. For these reasons, a modified Bonar scale is currently being developed that includes a correlation between the patient's clinical characteristics and tendon changes.

During the research process, it was not possible to determine the histomorphological changes in the long head of the biceps tendon in the preoperative period of patients who underwent surgery. Therefore, only with relative indicators can it be assumed that degenerative processes occur in the tendon structure even in the pre-rupture period.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the histopathology of the tendon in patients who underwent tenodesis after the rupture of the long head of the biceps tendon showed chronic degenerative changes with minimal inflammation using the Bonar scoring system. This confirms that the histopathology is more consistent with tendinosis rather than tendinitis. In the postoperative period, all patients showed good to excellent results. No clear correlation was found between the surgical outcomes and the Bonar scale results.

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